

FIBER-METAL LAMINATES, WORKSHOP PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

With the growing interest of the industry in the fatigue resistant Fiber-metal Laminates, suitable forming and machining need to be developed. This report focuses on the typical properties of the laminates and their influence on the formability and machinability. Several manufacturing techniques are discussed in detail. Two examples, proving the manufacturability of Fiber-metal Laminates, are presented.

1: Introduction

"Fiber-metal laminates" (F.M.L.) consist of alternating aluminium sheets and fiber/epoxy prepreg layers. The epoxy resin also provides the adhesive bonding of the layers (fig.1). The name "Fiber-metal Laminates" points at a complete family of sheet materials. Aluminium layers used are Al-2024-T3, Al-7075-T6 and Al-7475-T761 (thickness 0,2, 0.3 mm or 0.4 mm). The prepreg layers contain aramid, glass or carbon fibers, embedded in the AF-163 resin, produced by 3M. Fibers are orientated Uni Directional (UD) or bidirectional, a Cross Ply (CP). In a CP-laminate fibers can be divided over the two directions equally, 50/50%, or in a 70/30% ratio. Different lay-ups can be assembled (notation: $x/x-1$, = number of aluminium / number of prepreg layers).

Because of the crack bridging effect (fig.2), preventing cracks from opening, F.M.Laminates show superior fatigue properties. This, in combination with a high specific tensile strength, a good damage tolerance and an excellent fire resistance, make them candidates for both primary and secondary structures. Since, for modern airplanes, the need to prevent or find cracks in an early stage, strongly affects both the design and the length of inspection intervals and their costs, the aircraft industry shows great interest in these laminates. However manufacturing aircraft structures demands suitable forming and

Fig.1: Different configurations of a 3/2 layup.

Fig2: Crack bridging of fibers in a F.M.-Laminate.

machining processes. Until now forming and machining results were obtained by "trial and error." To overcome this stage a research project was started at Delfts University approaching the workshop properties more systematically. In this paper the latest developments are discussed.

2: Forming Fiber-metal Laminates

At first glance a F.M.Laminate looks like a conventional monolithic metal sheet. However, paragraphs 2.1 to 2.9 discuss several differences in material behaviour, one should be aware of to avoid disappointing forming results. If models are available, describing the influence on the formability, references are given.

In a unidirectional laminate two main directions can be distinguished, the longitudinal (L) direction, parallel to the fibers, and the longitudinal transverse (LT) direction, perpendicular to the fibers. In a C.P.laminate the two main directions coincide with the fiber directions.

2.1 The definition of material properties of Fiber-metal Laminates.

Laminates are often treated as sheet materials, expecting them to have material properties independent of the thickness or the layout. Actually they are constructions, built up from different materials. The properties of a construction depend on the material properties of its constituents and on the way it is constructed. For F.M.Laminates for example, the stiffness of a 3/2 lay-up exceeds the stiffness of a 4/3 lay-up, because of the increase of the volume percentage of the aluminium.

Nevertheless laminates are simple constructions. The residual stresses, discussed in paragraph 2.6, are the only complicating aspect. However, taking these into consideration, still simple formulas can be derived (v.Hengel, ref.1), resulting in the properties of the laminate in the two main directions.

2.2 The anisotropic behaviour of Fiber-metal Laminates.

Looking at their configuration it is obvious that F.M.Laminates, especially the U.D.laminates, show strong anisotropy. Next to the wide variety of configurations the anisotropy gives the designer the possibility to suit the material to its purpose. However forming operations become more complicated. Although the exact influence of the anisotropy in complex forming operations is not yet known, some general affects are discussed here.

In several products the fiber direction is related to the geometry. Figure 3 shows a blank and a formed conus shape. After unloading, the springback will vary over the height of the conus. Furthermore, the structural properties of a formed conus are not rotation symmetric. The same effects can be recognized in shrink or stretch flanges.

In conventional sheet forming strain limits are given by a forming limit diagram. When failure strains are plotted as a function of the strain e_2 , measured perpendicular to e_1 , one curve, a so called forming limit curve, is obtained. For conventional metal sheets the curve can be regarded as a material property. For the anisotropic F.M.Laminates failure strains depend on the load direction. An e_1 - e_2 diagram would contain an infinite amount of curves, each presenting a set of critical strain combinations, related to only one direction. In reality failures are generally found in one of the main directions. Therefore two curves, presenting these extremes, are of special interest. Verloop (ref.2) developed methods to determine these extremes both theoretical and practical. Figure 4 presents these extremes in a e_1 - e_2 diagram for a typical F.M.Laminate.

Fig.3: Fiber orientation in a conical shaped product, before and after forming.

2.3 The ultimate tensile strain of Fiber-metal Laminates.

The ultimate tensile strain of a laminate in L-direction is equal to the ultimate strain of the fibers. For the commonly used fiber systems ultimate strains are comparatively small. (glass $\pm 4.5\%$, carbon $\pm 1.5\%$, aramid $\pm 1.75\%$). Except for extreme small fiber volume percentages fiber failure directly causes complete failure of the laminate.

The aluminium dominates the ultimate strain in LT-direction. The fibers however reduce the contraction in L-direction. Therefore in a tensile test, the aluminium is not loaded in plane stress, as is usually the case, but in a nearly plane strain condition. This reduces the ultimate strain. For example, the failure strain of monolithic Al 2024-T3 is $\pm 18\%$, for a laminate, based on 2024-T3, in LT-direction it is $\pm 10\%$.

2.4 The Compressive Properties of Fiber-metal Laminates.

If compressive properties are concerned one cannot speak of F.M.Laminates in general. Aramid fibers offer very poor compressive properties (ref.3). A local shear type of failure damages the fibers permanently after 0.5% compressive deformation, reducing the laminates overall performance. Arall (Aramid reinforced laminate) should not be loaded in compression during forming operations.

Fig.4: An e_1 - e_2 diagram for a typical F.M.laminate.

Glass fibers offer better compressive properties. For supported Glare (glass reinforced laminate) specimen compressive strains over 2.0% were obtained (ref.4). The failure of the fibers is of a shear type, directly followed by buckling of the aluminium layers. Unsupported laminates were not tested yet. The separated thin layers are barely capable of carrying any compressive loads. Therefore the compressive properties of a laminate depend on the bonding quality, especially its capability to carry peel stresses at the interfaces. Depending on the unsupported length, the material stiffness, the clamping mode and the bonding quality either buckling of the complete laminate (as a conventional sheet) or buckling of the separate layers is expected. Possibly before any plastic deformation has occurred. Special attention should be paid to the support of the laminate if compressive loads occur in a forming operation. When possible compressive deformations should be avoided.

2.5 The elastic behaviour of the fibers in a Fiber-metal Laminates.

During forming the fibers behave purely elastic until failure. Two effects result from this.

First, stretching or compressive operations in L-direction result in a considerable build up of elastic energy. As a consequence the springback will be large. Because, in bending operations, the extend in which fibers are stretched or compressed relates to their position, relative to the neutral axis, springback depends on the way the laminate is stacked. For the design of tools the prediction of springback is important. Maas (ref.5) developed an accurate analytical model, predicting the springback of F.M.Laminates after straight line bending.

Techniques, developed for monolithic metals, to reduce springback after bending, are not always suitable for F.M.Laminates. Squeezing for example, in the final phase of a 90° V-die bend, only reduces the springback related to the aluminium layers.

Secondly, once a certain strain is exceeded in L-direction glass-fibers have stored enough energy to plastically deform the aluminium during unloading. Figure 5 illustrates this. Although the

Fig.5: A typical stress strain curve of a F.M.laminate.

shear stresses at the edges (figure 7). Kappel (ref.5) examined and modelled this phenomena, deriving formulas for both the maximum shear stress and the distribution of the stresses.

Stretching or compression operations have influence on the internal residual stress system. For example, since tensile stresses in the outer aluminium layer are unfavourable for the fatigue properties of laminates, the internal stress system, in as cured state, is reversed by pre-stretching. Figure 6 illustrates the effect of stretching on the residual stresses in an U.D-laminate. Notice that part of the formability is used by prestretching.

2.7 Delamination in Fiber-metal Laminates as an extra failure mode.

During forming operations, the applied forming loads might introduce extra interlaminar peel or shear stresses. During bending for example the outer layer is stretched, introducing tensile stresses, while the inner layer is compressed, introducing compressive stresses into the flange. To maintain an equilibrium shear stresses occur in the interfaces of the flange (fig.8a). If the maximum allowed shear or peel stress in any of the interfaces or the ultimate strain in the resin is exceeded, delamination will occur (fig 8b). The maximum allowed shear and peel stresses depend on the bonding quality. Both the fibers and the aluminium are pretreated. The "Adhesive Institute", established at Delfts University of Technology, is looking at new pretreatments for the aluminium layers, increasing bonding quality and friendly to the environment.

ultimate strain of glass fibers is $\pm 4.5\%$ the residual strain in a tensile test is no more then 1.5%. For complex parts springback might reduce, because of the structural stiffness of the part (ref 2). For a sphere residual strains in fiber direction of almost 4.5% were obtained.

2.6 Interlaminar residual stresses in Fiber-metal Laminates

Two features cause residual stresses in laminated structures. F.M.Laminates are subjected to a bonding cycle at an elevated temperature (120°). Since the coefficients of expansion of the different layers do not match, cooling down results in thermal residual stresses. In the "as cured" state in fiber direction the aluminium layers are loaded in tension, the fiber layers in compression (figure 6). The residual stresses are introduced into the layers by interlaminar

Fig 6: Residual stresses in F.M.Laminates.

Fig.7: Shear stresses at the edge due to the residual stresses in a laminate.

2.8 Heat treatments for Fiber-metal Laminates.

F.M.Laminates cannot be heat-treated. The resin will not stand temperatures, at which an aluminium is heat-treated. A decrease in bonding quality, and therefore its capability to carry the interlaminar shear stresses, causes delamination.

2.9 Strain rate effects in forming Fiber-metal Laminates

Fig.8a: Shear stresses in the flange due to bending.

The ultimate strain, ultimate stress and E-modulus of the resin, and possible some properties of the fibers too, depend on the strain rate. Bending tests clearly show improved results, to be specific, smaller obtainable minimum bend radii, at lower forming speeds. On the other hand the results presented by Vlot (ref.7) suggest an increased ultimate strain in L-direction in a tensile test, at extremely high forming speeds, for both glass/epoxy prepregs and Glare. Although no large scale research has been performed yet strain rate effects will be investigated in the near future.

2.10 Suitable forming processes for Fiber-metal Laminates.

Although the properties of the laminates, discussed in paragraph 2.1 to 2.9 might suggest a need for new forming techniques, many conventional processes have been used successfully. Not the forming techniques but the obtainable product complexity is affected most when F.M.Laminates are formed. This indicates a need for optimal use of the forming capacities of F.M.Laminates.

Fig.8b: Delamination due to bending.

The layered structure can even become an advantage. Sinke (ref.8) manufactured thick profiles with smaller minimum bend radii then can be obtained for comparative monolithic aluminium profiles, by assembling pre-formed elements. Breugel (ref.9) used this technique to manufacture complex deep drawn components.

The manufacturing of many components imply bending procedures. Three roll bending has successfully been used to produce single curved components with large radii, like for example fuselage components. Springback is no problem since it can easily be compensated for on line. For small radii press brake bending is suitable. Because of the strong springback a V-die is not recommended. After unloading the relation between the shape of the die and the bend angle gets lost. When an U-die is used, the final shape can be affected by control of the stroke. Bending with small radii is often used to produce stringers. To meet structural demands, unidirectional laminates are used with fibers in the longitudinal direction of the stringer. Therefore during bending strains occur perpendicular to the fiber direction, and obtained radii are comparable to aluminium.

Conventional steel molds can be used. However it is not optimal to introduce the bending moment by high local forces. Bending results will improve if elastomeric pads are used, offering a more uniform load distribution. The shape of the rubber pad can be adapted to optimize bending and friction forces.

Rubber pressing has successfully been performed to form flanges, collared holes, joggles and stiffening beads. Deep drawing implies compressive deformations in the flange. Therefore the obtainable complexity is very limited. Stretch forming offers better perspectives. Future plans involve the testing of less conventional forming processes as peen forming, creepforming and high energy rate forming on F.M.Laminates.

3: Machining of Fiber-metal Laminates.

Many known machining processes were performed on F.M.Laminates. Although a large scale research has been set up at the university of Delft, aiming at the optimisation of drilling, milling and waterjet cutting, results are not available yet. In the next paragraphs the machining properties of F.M.Laminates are listed, mainly based on experiences gained in preliminary test.

First the difference between aramid and glass or carbon fibers is discussed. Glass and carbon fibers are very hard and abrasive. Tools wear out relatively fast. Although blunt cutting edges can still cut glass or carbon fibers the increase in cutting force and heat production might cause delamination. Aramid fibers are of a softer, but very tough type. Arall is very susceptible to even the slightest wear of the cutting edge. Slightly blunt cutting edges tend to pull the fibers out of the resin instead of cutting them. Therefore Arall laminates might have hairy edges. The quality of the edge is not influenced by this phenomena.

3.1 Cutting Fiber-metal Laminates

Cutting and piercing are performed on a guillotine type of press. First very high local forces, applied by the cutting edges, indent the material. Because of the indentation the cross section decreases. Secondly the still increasing force causes the cross section to fail by shearing. The depth of the indentation just before shear failure occurs, increases with increasing material thickness, decreasing sharpness of the cutting edge and increasing gap wideness between the knives, causing the upper fiber layers to stretch. Therefore when thick laminates are cut with blunt or damaged cutting edges the upper layer might delaminate. If the sheet is insufficiently supported delamination at the bottom layer occurs (fig 9).

Fig.9: Delamination due to insufficient support.

3.2 Sawing Fiber-metal Laminates.

Sawing is a good alternative for cutting thick laminates (> 2.0 mm). Since forces are working perpendicular to the plane of the sheet, laminates need good support at the bottom side. Saw blades tend to follow the fiber direction. Therefore, if a straight cut is needed parallel to the fiber direction, the saw blade needs good lateral support. Again fiber pull out (Arall) or increased tool wear (Glare) can be observed.

3.3 Waterjet Cutting Fiber-metal Laminates.

Waterjet cutting is one of the most promising cutting techniques for F.M.Laminates. Laminates, in several thicknesses, have been waterjet cut successfully. The major advantage of this process is the decreased heat production and tool wear. Entering a laminate with a waterjet asks for special attention. No problems are detected when the waterjet enters the material at one of the edges. When cutting starts in the center of a sheet, the upper layer might delaminate before the waterjet penetrates the material completely. The oncoming stream pushes the waterjet aside, pressing the layers apart. A large scale test program, performed at the University of Delft, aims at the optimization of the process for F.M.Laminates.

3.4 Drilling Fiber-metal Laminates.

Good quality holes can be drilled in F.M.Laminates using conventional drills. As mentioned the tools need to be sharp. Driving forces increase as the cutting edge quality decreases. Since only a small edge of the outside layer carries the driving force, when the bit almost completely penetrates the material, the outer layer might delaminate from the substrate (fig.10). Proper support at the backside, drilling with a constant feed rate or damping the exit forces, allowing only a limited acceleration of the tool bit at exit, can solve these problems.

Fig.10: Push out and pull up delamination during drilling.

Occasionally a second type of failure can be observed as the quality of the cutting edge decreases. The pull up forces, removing the chips, cause pull up delamination (fig 10). Since push out delamination occurs in an earlier stage, no real effort has yet been made to solve this problem.

The problem of ovalization, due to the release of internal stresses, can be solved by a second drilling operation. Deburring can be performed as for conventional aluminium.

3.5 Routing Fiber-metal Laminates.

Routing is used to produce narrow tolerated blanks from thin sheet materials. To minimize the chance on delamination, forces perpendicular to the plane of the laminate should be prevented. Consequently, the best results are obtained with straight flute mills.

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Since the layers react to the machining operation differently, the acting forces change over the thickness of the laminate (fig 11). As a consequence interlaminar shear stresses occur in the interfaces. For Glare the part of the cutting edge cutting the fibers wears out much faster than the part cutting the aluminium. The difference in the applied loads and the increased heat production might result in premature delamination. For Arall a slight increase of the tool wear dramatically increases the forces acting on the fiber layer, while hardly influencing the aluminium. Again this might result in delamination.

Fig.11: Forces acting on the laminate edge during milling operations.

A longitudinal translation of the mill will result in the use of a yet unaffected part of the cutting edge. This results in a longer tool life. Thin laminates or stacks need support at both sides. Even for thick laminates the changes on delamination reduce as the outer layers are supported.

3.6 Suitable machining processes for Fiber-metal Laminates.

Fig.12: The cargo door of the C-17 carrier.

Again all tested machining techniques appeared to be suitable. In milling or drilling operations for Glare feed rates and number of revolutions should be chosen as for conventional aluminium. The same counts for Arall, although sometimes higher speeds are recommended. Conventional cooling and lubricating fluids should be used whenever possible, to reduce the cutting forces and the heat production. Grinding, although not too long on the same spot (heat production!!), and the use of abrasive paper are allowed. Laserjet cutting is not yet tested on F.M.Laminates. It is expected that the excessive heat production will cause delamination.

At present, research at the university of Delft is aiming at optimizing the geometry of the tools, the feed rate, the cutting speed and on decreasing the tool wear (diamond coated tool bits).

4: Two examples of components that required manufacturing processes.

Figure 10 presents the C-17 cargo door, a heavily loaded structure of 9 by 5.5 meters. It is the largest component, produced of F.M.Laminates, that is installed in an operational airplane. The door was designed in Arall and shows a 26% weight saving over conventional aluminium, without significantly affecting either costs or schedule of the C-17 program. The cargo door application proved the manufacturability of F.M.Laminates. It requires stretch forming, roll forming, routing, bonding and riveting operations.

Figure 11 presents several examples of cold formed parts produced from Arall or Glare. The stringer-frame-skin combination was produced using different laminate configurations, adapted to the structural functions. The components were manufactured using routing, drilling, three roll bending, stretch-forming, and rubber pad forming techniques (ref. 10).

Fig.13: Several cold formed parts, produced from F.M.Laminates.

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